

GR4FITE3

Graphite resilience for lithium-ion battery anodes via sustainable European end-to-end supply chain

We create a whole new supply chain to achieve a more efficient production of lithium-ion batteries in Europe for use in electric vehicles and energy storage systems applications for solar and wind farms.

Join us on our journey as we trace a greener path from Zavalievsky Graphite LCC, the largest operating natural graphite mine in Europe, through to the laboratories where lithium-ion battery materials are characterised.

Keep up with the project

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